

ESTABLISHING A NEW SEMINAR TO COMBINE LEARNING ABOUT TECHNOLOGY AND SOCIETY

U. Berbuir¹

Ruhr-University Bochum
Bochum, Germany
ORCID: 0000-0003-4451-0128

Conference Key Areas: *Sustainability and Ethics in Engineering Education, Teaching methods*

Keywords: *Problem Based Learning, Public Participation, online collaboration, Interdisciplinarity*

ABSTRACT

For the transformation we face in industry and society, a broad societal consensus and collaboration between different stakeholders are vitally important. With this in mind, the Environmental Engineering program focuses on environmentally relevant technical developments and the consideration of systemic interrelationships while incorporating societal frameworks.

The recently implemented course Technology – Dialogue – Society was developed as an introduction to these complex tasks for first-year students. It focusses on topics of the energy transition sector and public participation. The learning objectives of the course are the acquisition of methodological competencies as well as the promotion of communication, teamwork and the ability to reflect. An overarching goal of the course is also onboarding of students in the program.

A wide set of teaching-learning methods is used to achieve this broad objectives. In addition to lectures, collaborative and dialogue-oriented teaching-learning methods such as problem-based learning, peer review of student work, conversational simulations and reflection assignments are used. A particular challenge of

¹ *Corresponding Author*

ute.berbuir@rub.de

implementation was the course size of approximately 100 students and the need for online teaching due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

The structure of the course is described and the evaluation results of the first run are presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In light of the climate crisis, issues of sustainability and rapid decarbonization of our energy supply are becoming increasingly urgent. The changes required go hand in hand with fundamental social and technical transformations that can only succeed if technical developments are also socially viable. Precisely because engineers are the ones who develop and implement technology, awareness of societal problems and interrelationships is also of particular importance to them and should be integrated into engineering curricula.

As part of the restructuring of the Environmental Engineering program (formerly Environmental Engineering and Resource Management), a new module was developed and integrated in the curriculum to address these challenges in the program. A particular goal of the module is that students are confronted with this kind of profession-related topics from the very beginning and experience the consideration of societal concerns as belonging to the subject.

The module consists of two parts: The first part, the course *technology - dialogue - society (TDS)* deals with challenges and methods of public participation in industrial and infrastructure projects. The construction or reconstruction of infrastructure as well as the use of technologies is always accompanied by questions of acceptance. In Germany (as in many other countries), there are increasingly massive disputes about the realization of energy transition projects like wind turbines and transmission grids. Finding viable solutions and creating acceptance is a task for society as a whole [1] and this challenge is a well-suited topic to promote the necessary attitudes and competencies in an engineering course.

The second part, the course *environmental ethics for engineers*, focuses on philosophical methods and the analysis of environmental ethical issues. This paper presents the design of the TDS-course and discusses the results of the first run.

1.2 Goals of the TDS-course

The TDS-course deals with environmentally relevant technical issues and social application references. Solving such complex problems requires a variety of knowledge as well as personal and social skills, such as communication skills and the ability to work together in an interdisciplinary manner. These personal and social competencies should be fostered in the course and the development of values and attitude should be stimulated.

The content-focused learning objectives are the acquisition of technical and methodological skills for public participation. The Association of German Engineers (VDI) has developed a guideline that provides support for organisations in the planning, organisation and execution of early public participation, as well as recommendations in the form of a structured process [2]. The methods taught in the course refer to this standard.

This broad set of learning objectives aims at developing competencies based on the T-shaped model [4] and the Future Skills concept. "*Future Skills* are competences that allow individuals to solve complex problems in highly emergent contexts of action in a self-organised way and enable them to act (successfully). They are based on cognitive, motivational, volitional and social resources, are value-based and can be acquired in a learning process." [5] Obviously, these competencies cannot be covered comprehensively or at a high level in such an introductory course, but serious engagement can be initiated and an awareness of the approaches and importance of these competencies and topics can be fostered.

With regard to the observation, that students who do not have a positive experience with social transition at the university have greater difficulty coping with the challenges of the first year of study [6], this course is also intended to promote arrival at the university. This aspect became particularly important in the first run due to the Corona contact-restrictions and limited opportunities for social interaction on the campus.

2 STRUCTURE AND DIDACTIC ELEMENTS OF THE TDS-COURSE

The objectives explained above were transformed into a course concept under the following framework conditions. The TDS-course is a required course in the first semester of the Environmental Engineering degree program and encompasses a workload of 2 credits. The number of expected participants, based on the number of new students, has fluctuated between 50 and 120 in recent years.

The development of the TDS-course is based on the experience with the topic of public participation from interdisciplinary seminars for advanced students and the successful use of problem-based learning (PBL) and conversational simulations therein [3]. The PBL-method forms a core element in this new course as well and the case work drives the thematic discussion and structures the weekly sessions. Problem-based learning (Maastricht model) is process-oriented, promotes communicative skills and collaboration, encourages reflection, and is very well suited to deal with interdisciplinary tasks [7]. Case studies from everyday (work-) life are the starting point. These are worked on in groups and the PBL-process takes place in predetermined steps:

- Case analysis and derivation of research tasks in the group
- Research phase (usually until the next session)
- Presentation and discussion of the results in the group, development of solution approaches and feedback [8, 9]

Experiences with the use of PBL with student groups that are not familiar with this form of learning show that it is very helpful for students to receive a relatively high level of content support and reflection. Therefore, basic knowledge is conveyed in short lectures (30 min) or instructional videos and the results and solution approaches from the group case work are also reflected on again in the plenary.

Since students in the first semester have little experience with scientific work, feedback on their writing is very important. Therefore, a peer review of the students' research questions was introduced as an additional step. This is handled via the Moodle learning platform. The peer review offers the great advantage that the students also change into the role of the commentator. They see the work of their fellow students and have to give feedback on certain criteria. Furthermore, they receive feedback on their own work.

The problem-oriented approach is continued during the two seminar sessions, the format also encompasses. These seminars serves as an exemplary application of learned methods. It is also a deep dive into communication situations that occur in public participation. In the second seminar a participation format will be carried out as a simulated conversation (role play). The structure of the course is shown in Figure 1.

Fig.1. Structure of TDS-course

In line with the methods, different types of written performance are required:

- - Elaborations on the "own" PBL research questions.
- - Peer reviews on elaborations by other students
- - Written reflections on findings, processes, or discussions.

In the run-up of this course it was intensively discussed in which form the learning process can be secured and whether and how the performance of the students could be measured. The learning objectives focus on the development of personal and social competencies. Measuring such competencies is generally demanding and time-consuming. Taking into consideration that the course is also about raising awareness for complex issues and stimulating personal development, testing and grading seems counterproductive. Like Reimann says, rather "*potential educational spaces*" are needed: "However, these can only unfold if not every performance shown (and not shown) is recorded and evaluated" [10]. In addition, the course is also intended to support onboarding. Therefore, the course does not include a traditional exam or grading. The workload is secured by checking and documenting the weekly work assignments.

3 IMPLEMENTATION

The first run of the course took place under two special conditions. First, a high number of students from the third or fifth semester of the former study program, who had switched to the modified program, were obligated to attend according to examination law. Their share of the total number of student participants was about 50%. The second special condition is that, due to the pandemic, it had to be conducted entirely as online-remote teaching.

About 100 students participated in the course. They were divided into 14 groups of 6-8 participants. As shown in Figure 1, the weekly Zoom Online sessions consisted of different phases. They usually began with a short plenary lecture. Then, students worked on PBL cases in breakout sessions in their groups. At the end of the group-session, there was another plenary phase in which the results were reflected on together and the work assignments for the following week were concretized.

At the beginning of the course, the objectives and methods were made transparent and in particular the PBL method was explained and practiced. Extensive templates were provided in the online whiteboard Miro for collaborative processing of the tasks. With the help of the pre-structured templates, the students were able to work autonomously in the group phases, i.e. without tutorial guidance. In case of questions, tutors were available in the plenum. Students had a work assignment to complete by each of the weekly deadlines during the current semester. The assignments were uploaded to or worked on in the accompanying course on the learning platform Moodle.

In addition to the weekly meetings, two seminars took place. The first seminar was conducted with one group and lasted two hours each. In the second seminar, three

groups were combined. In this four-hour seminar, students assumed specific stakeholder roles and simulated participation situations.

4 EXPERIENCES, EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

Overall, the implementation of this methodologically complex and organizationally extensive course worked well. 104 people registered and 99 successfully completed the course. From the teachers point of view, it was possible to create a good working atmosphere in which an intensive exchange was possible. On the basis of the submitted work assignments, the documented work processes and results in the Miro-Boards and the high level of commitment in the two seminars, we can conclude that a comprehensive examination of the topics took place. Basic knowledge and methods were acquired, which all groups were able to demonstrate, especially in the two seminars. Nevertheless, the level of goal achievement varies on the individual level.

Student evaluation of the course was assessed using a standardized questionnaire of the faculty of mechanical engineering. A total of 92 students participated in the evaluation and the course was rated good to very good overall. (mw: 4.5 on a scale of 1-5 (5 = very good) N=92)

The students' responses to open-ended questions are particularly revealing. More than 50 students described in their own words what they particularly liked about the course and where they see potential for improvement. For a differentiated analysis, the students' responses were split into individual statements and these were then assigned to thematic categories. The numbers of mentions per category are shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2 Evaluation outcomes: Number of mentions per category

The high number of comments suggests that the course has succeeded in engaging students well and that a good level of ownership of the course has emerged. This is also matched by the observation that the comments on the potential for improvement were all constructively formulated and appropriate in terms of content.

The analysis of the free text fields shows that many participants especially liked the group work in the course. More than a quarter of the students explicitly name the group or the group work as *"a highlight of the course"*. The good and open atmosphere in the course is also mentioned as particularly positive.

Suggestions for improvement often relate to organizational aspects, such as the scheduling of seminars or implementation problems in the Moodle course, which should be improved in the next run. Further suggestions concern the wish that the seminars should take place face-to-face on campus - which hopefully can be realized in the future.

About a quarter of the participants explicitly described the methods of the course as particularly good. Students frequently remark that a good mix of methods was used and that this type of teaching was inspiring. The topic of public participation and dealing with societal challenges such as the acceptance of the energy transition are described as interesting and important.

However, individual differences are also apparent from the comments. While some participants would have liked clearer guidelines, less group work and more input, others call for the exact opposite, i.e. less input and more group work. These different assessments can be attributed to personal preferences on the one hand, and group effects on the other hand. Depending on the composition of the group, different dynamics can develop that have a significant impact on cooperation and learning. This is also evident in the individual responses. While some students regret that there was sometimes little talk in the group, others say that they *"had a lot of fun"*, *"rarely met such dedicated people"* and had a *"very motivated and friendly group"*. But even with a less motivated group, the course was considered to be successful: *"Unfortunately, my group wasn't very communicative ... but it worked out anyway"*.

Special condition: no written exam. There were also comments on this topic. These were mostly positive, such as *"I felt like I was attending the course to learn something and not, as in other courses, just to get my certificate of achievement..."*. Two comments criticized the fact that there was no written exam at the end. The lack of the self-disciplining effect of an exam was referred to as a negative one, and another student pointed out a danger of *"cheating through"*.

Particularly interesting is students' view on the amount of work. With regard to the amount of credit points this was seen as appropriate by most students, but is estimated as too high by some. In particular, the extensive research tasks are criticized for being too time-consuming. It is clear that in this course students' own motivation is of great importance. But this can also be seen as an opportunity. The question is whether the majority of the students worked continuously and used this

opportunity. In this regard the comparison with other courses is interesting. From the faculty's area-wide course evaluation aggregated comparative data is available. In the answers to the question *"I regularly prepare/review the session/work units"*, the TDS-course actually scores slightly better with a value of 3.6 (agreement on a scale of 5) in comparison to the average in the mechanical engineering courses value of 3.3.

What also became clear in reviewing the feedback is that for some students participation in the course helped quite explicitly in arriving at their studies in dealing with distance teaching: *"I was part of a really motivated and sympathetic group that I will continue to work with. In this Corona time, this has been very helpful for me."*, *"The TDS-course has also been an anchor point for me in an otherwise spongy asynchronous semester and has helped me structurally as a result."*

5 SUMMARY

This paper describes the structure and experiences of the first run of a course for first-year students in environmental engineering. Using the example of acceptance problems in energy transition projects, technical and societal issues are discussed and methods of public participation are addressed.

The teaching concept has proven to be viable for a group of around 100 participants and was conducted entirely online in the first run. Through the use of various coordinated collaborative teaching methods, it has been achieved that the students have intensively dealt with different perspectives of energy transition projects. The students have systematically worked together in groups and comprehensively reflected on their work results. The openness of the course, which was also due to the fact that there was no assessment and grading at the end, was very positively received and engaged by the vast majority of students. The course was also able to make a valuable contribution to students onboarding.

REFERENCES

- [1] Oppermann, B. and Renn, O. (2019), Partizipation und Kommunikation in der Energiewende, Schriftenreihe Energiesysteme der Zukunft, München.
- [2] Verein Deutscher Ingenieure (2015), VDI 7000 Early public participation in industrial and infrastructure projects, Düsseldorf
- [3] Berbuir, U. and John, M. (2020), Not in my backyard – industrial and Infrastructure projects in an engineering education course, International Research Symposium on PBL, Guerra, A., Chen, J., Winther, M., & Kolmos, A. (Eds.), Aalborg Universitetsforlag, pp. 99-109
- [4] Medhat, S. and Peers, S. (2012), A White Paper: T-shaped Learning for the New Technologist, <https://stemfoundation.org.uk/asset/resource/%7B3EA5228A-B620-4783-AE91-190F2C182DAA%7D/resource.pdf>

- [5] Ehlers, U.-D. (2020), *Future Skills: The Future of Learning and Higher Education*, 1. Auflage. BoD - Books on Demand, Norderstedt, p. 53.
- [6] Kantanis, T. (2000), The role of social transition in students': adjustment to the first-year of university, *Journal of Institutional Research*, 9(1), pp.100-110.
- [7] Kolmos A. and Graaff E. de (2014), Problem-Based and Project-Based Learning in Engineering Education. In: Johri, A., Olds, B. (eds) *Cambridge Handbook of Engineering Education Research*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, pp. 141-160.
- [8] Berbuir, U., Lieverscheidt H. and Slemeyer A. (2014), Problemorientiertes Lernen. *duz Deutsche Universitätszeitung*, pp. 73–75.
- [9] Barrett, T. (2006), Understanding Problem–Based Learning, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242683636_Understanding_problem-based_learning
- [10] Reimann, G., (2014), Kompetenzorientierung und Prüfungspraxis an Universitäten: Ziele heute und früher, Problemanalyse und ein unzeitgemäßer Vorschlag, https://gabi-reinmann.de/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/Artikel_Berlin_Okt_14.pdf